
D 7.1 Project Communication and Dissemination Plan

Task 7.1. Dissemination and communication strategy
WP7 Project Outreach

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 7.1 is related to WP7 Project Outreach. This document is concerned with developing the dissemination and communication concept for the crossCert project detailing the objectives and planned activities for the duration of the project. The concept is to ensure a targeted, continuous and structured flow of information to stakeholders and to users of Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) in order to increase and maintain stakeholders' interest and awareness. Dissemination is a continuous activity during the whole project. All relevant results will be distributed in accordance with the dissemination concept. The main objective of all dissemination and communication activities is to increase the expected impact among the target audience, to engage with additional stakeholders and to put the crossCert on the agenda of relevant stakeholders. This deliverable contains not only a dissemination strategy but also the specific steps dedicated to the work plan, distribution of responsibilities, definition of channels with dedicated communication and dissemination (C&D) tools.

To raise awareness for the project, dissemination activities are extremely relevant for this project during its whole lifecycle and beyond. While the dissemination's main approach is sharing the achievements of the project, the communication develops methods in and beyond the process of dissemination of the results. crossCert Communication provides information to convey the project's key messages through a variety of channels using digital and printed materials, based on the crossCert corporate design with a specific logo, colours and fonts. To present crossCert to the outside world, project partners have the option to use websites, online portals, newsletters, social media channels, press releases as well as documents created in templates for reports and presentations. There will also be a template for the newsletter. An overview of dissemination methods describe the ways we aim to raise awareness, inform the audience, to engage with target groups and to promote the project. This will be followed by explanatory subsections with roadmaps and KPIs.

The consortium implements classic C&D tools mixed with contemporary communication to build the image of crossCert, increase knowledge and use publicity tools. Networking, Target group relations and dialogue with stakeholder groups via communication channels are used to reach our dissemination and communication goals.

The crossCert project consortium plans to reach a specific set of target groups by combining scientific and non-scientific presentations with online media. At relevant milestones of the project, partners will reach out to their contacts to provide crossCert project related content. While the main hub of the crossCert project will be the crossCert website as a reference point, with access to the benchmark repositories, internet-based EPC Knowledge Exchange Centre and online PR will support dialogue and consultation with the stakeholders of the project. Social online community building will support content delivery, promoting the idea of peer support and involvement of stakeholders. Communication activities are designed using the 'Goals - Audience - Messages - Tools - Tactics' approach, identifying and describing these for the whole project, parts of the project and for the deliverables/outcomes that require dissemination.

This deliverable is structured in three chapters to provide a detailed plan on how the partnership intends to reach its main dissemination objective.

The first chapter, dissemination and communication concept outlines the purpose of dissemination, the target groups, the key messages tailored to target groups, the responsibilities of all the involved partners and the main channels. The target audience unites a variety of different stakeholders we intend to reach: Academia and research communities, Experts and Policy-makers. While the Dissemination strategy explains the main approach for sharing the achievements of the project, the Communication

strategy describes the development of the communication methods in and beyond the process of dissemination of the results.

The second chapter gives an overview about how the project intends to implement the concept, giving an overview of the materials, methods and activity plan. Chapter 2 also provides an overview of the supporting dissemination and communication materials like style guide and corporate design, templates, posters, etc. Furthermore, it presents the used communication methods with a focus on the purpose of dissemination and outreach. We will use methods e.g., newsletters, press releases or social media to raise awareness, to inform the target audience, to engage with target groups and to promote the project. The steps to increase our outreach by using all our dissemination and communication methods are detailed according to channels, giving a detailed picture of how each dissemination and communication material is planned to reach its relevant target groups in order to generate followers.

The third chapter gives a detailed view on the expected impacts of dissemination and communication based on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and elaborates on the methods of monitoring the activities. It illustrates how dissemination and communication impact is planned to be measured and which important factors have been identified to support its dissemination. By nature, dissemination, communication and engagement are closely related and therefore, measures for communication and engagement support dissemination (and vice versa).

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1	Communication and Dissemination Concept	8
1.1	Target Groups	10
1.2	Dissemination and Communication Objectives	11
1.3	Communication Goals	14
1.4	Communication Tools and Channels	15
	Collecting personal data via the project digital communication tools	15
	Video conferences and webinars via Zoom by Climate Alliance	15
	Content-based communication	15
1.5	Dissemination Tools and Channels	19
1.6	Tasks and Responsibilities	21
1.7	Time management	22
2	Implementation	24
2.1	Communication Strategy	24
	Obligatory acknowledgement of EU funding for all public outputs	24
	Global and local communication for crossCert	25
2.2	Visual Identity	26
2.3	Dissemination and Communication Activities	33
	Goals – Audience – Project Message – Tools – Tactics	33
2.3.1	Digital Channels: Websites	35
2.3.2	Digital Channel: Newsletters	36
2.3.3	Digital Channels: Social Media and Online Communities	39
	The project’s social media strategy	39
2.3.4	Public events: Engaging the experts and policy makers	41
	External Conferences and Events	43
2.3.5	Networking and Sister Projects	43
	Interaction with sister projects	45
	Joint Publications / exchange of articles	46
2.3.6	Publications	47
	Publication in magazines	47
	The Final Publication	47

Press Releases	48
3 Monitoring Communication and Dissemination Activities	49
3.1 Evaluation of the Impact	49
3.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	51
4 References	54
5 Annexes	56
Annex 1 Visual Identity Tools	56
Annex 2 Event Registration Consent to Processing of Personal Data	59
Annex 3 Event Report Template	62

INDEX OF TABLES

Table 1 Dissemination and Communication Objectives	12
Table 2 Public project results matched with channels and audience	16
Table 3 Communication methods paired with value for target groups	18
Table 4 Overview of dissemination channels	20
Table 5 C&D checkpoints per project phase	23
Table 6 Channels and Tools	34
Table 7 Newsletters Roadmap	37
Table 8 Networking Roadmap.....	46

1 Communication and Dissemination Concept

This document is supporting the communication and dissemination activities according to the Grant Agreement. The Annotated Model Grant Agreement article 38 informs about how communication and promoting the action should be done for Horizon 2020 actions and consulting the Online Manual for further information is suggested.

While the Dissemination strategy explains the main approach for sharing the achievements of the project, the Communication strategy describes the development of the communication methods in and beyond the process of dissemination of the results.

Overall, the purposes of dissemination and communication are:

- to raise awareness e.g., with social media in order to let others know what we do and to ensure maximum visibility of project key facts, objectives, activities, etc.
- to inform e.g., through newsletters, journal articles, reports, in order to educate the community,
- to engage e.g., through scientific presentations, stakeholder engagement events, webinars, conferences and policy events, meetings with stakeholders and liaising activities in order to get input and feedback from the community
- to promote e.g., crossCert website, conference presentations, events in order to showcase project outputs and results ([European Commission, Elaborating a Dissemination Plan, 30.01.2012](#)).

The dissemination plan was prepared under the management of the work package leader (WPL) Climate Alliance. The strategy has been developed in consultation with the coordinator and project partners. Project Partners were invited to contribute to this Deliverable. The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are defined in order to measure the effectiveness and impacts of the dissemination and communication tools and channels. All partners contribute to the dissemination strategy and plan through:

- Input in the discussions in the kick-off meeting and via the initial dissemination and communication survey,
- input to the dissemination and communication plan with own dissemination and communication channels,
- Review and comments on the draft papers,
- Participating and organising meetings, events for dissemination and multipliers,
- Participating actively in sessions and workshops,
- Contributing project results through social media, project partners' websites, newsletters, and scientific articles,
- Contributing to the exchange of knowledge among European stakeholders on existing and new EPCs in several member states, disseminating information on a wide cross-certification exercise among European countries, and the internet-based EPC Knowledge Exchange Centre,
- Contribution to and dissemination of press releases,
- Participating at external events presenting relevant crossCert results.

Concrete outputs that will be communicated and disseminated among stakeholders:

1. **A benchmark repository.** Repository of curated building data, certificate results and, where available, measured performance results of buildings.
2. **Technical guidelines for the next generation of EPCs.** Recommendations to reduce the performance gap, to implement the new KPIs in the EPCs, to present the renovation measures to the building owner and to verify and control the EPC quality.
3. **Guidelines and tools for the exploitation of EPC data.** Recommendations to create databases for the exploitation of EPC's data, to link with new EPC's with energy audits and renovation roadmaps and to elaborate tools to improve the information that EPCs provide.
4. **Guidelines for people-centred EPCs.** Guidelines to a better user experience, to training and education of certified EPC issuers and to promotion of the new EPCs.
5. **Recommendations for the harmonisation of next generation EPCs.** Recommendations considering: technical performance, data exploitation and human factor.
6. **An EPC knowledge exchange centre,** A web-based repository of information on EPC approaches.
7. **An EPC community forum.**

Dissemination makes the results/outcomes of a project visible to the target groups and the stakeholders that can implement its results. Communication renders comprehensible all the activities and main results associated with a project close to all interested key actors.

The partners active in the Work Package (WP) will raise awareness and inform about the results and activities that take place throughout the project. This process is planned and organised at the beginning of the project through this Communication and Dissemination Plan that acts as a guideline for the entire consortium. It contains detailed activities and methods of dissemination described. Slight adjustments, coming from external conditions and circumstances unforeseen will be applied without missing the achievement of the initial goals and Deliverables set. To achieve this aim, communication and dissemination activities will be monitored throughout the project and will be reported in an interim and in a final report. The document is drawn in accordance with the Grant Agreement, specifying the communication channels to be used for each of the target groups identified, the concerns of each of the target groups, and the messages and the outputs to be sent to each of them. The plan includes the specific communication strategy in terms of awareness-raising and promotion of the project's exploitable results, along with scientific publications and outreach.

This deliverable contains not only a dissemination strategy but also the specific steps dedicated to work plans, distribution of responsibilities, definition of channels with dedicated communication and dissemination (C&D) tools.

1.1 Target Groups

It is indispensable to know how to reach and provide material understandable for and wanted by the target groups. In fact, successful dissemination starts from the needs of the target groups. Each C&D material shall be developed taking into consideration its stakeholders. The materials will aim to give hints about what best “catches the attention” of the people for whom the C&D-tools are developed. This document supports the project to meet the defined goals by engagement actions by each partner and a project-wide plan for engaging the followers. For this, the target audience, the message to deliver, the relevant methods and finally the value for the target audience is defined.

The main target groups for dissemination are:

- **EPC experts and their organisations**, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities,
- **Policy-makers** in the building and energy sector including public institutions with regulatory function on local, regional and national level,
- **EPC users** with no expert knowledge,
- **Academia and the research community.**

The complete list of target groups for dissemination and communication are as follows:

Stakeholders	People	Role	Relevance
Energy Agencies	EPC experts Building experts Energy efficiency experts	EPC scheme stakeholder: implementation Potential investors	The overall results of the project
Public authorities	EPC experts Building experts Energy efficiency experts Legal experts	EPC scheme stakeholder: regulation, implementation Potential Investors	The overall results of the project
Regional/National certification bodies	EPC experts Building experts Energy efficiency experts	EPC scheme stakeholder: regulation Potential investors	The overall results of the project Results of WP4, concerning concepts like one-stop-shops, data available in EPCs databases or delivering value to investors.

Sectoral associations (green building councils, NGOs)	EPC experts Building experts Energy efficiency experts	EPC scheme stakeholder,	WP4 or WP5 results depending on the focus.
Municipalities	Building and energy-related department staff, construction, public building department staff, certification-related departments staff	EPC scheme stakeholder: One-stop-shops, Implementation Potential investors as building owners	Results of WP4, concerning concepts like one-stop-shops, data available in EPCs databases or delivering value to investors.
Academia and Research Communities	Researchers, modellers, energy efficiency experts, building policy researchers	Further development stakeholder, scientific advisory role, scientific evidence provider, impact assessment role	The overall methodologies and analysis applied in this project and the results obtained
EPC users	Customers, Building owners, Service providers (EPC issuer) Landlords Tenants	User-centred design stakeholder, user role	Results of WP4 (available data in databases, improving the user experience, one-stop-shops) and the overall results of WP5.
Companies, local communities		EPCs investors: commercial	Results of WP4, concerning concepts like one-stop-shops, data available in EPCs databases or delivering value to investors.

1.2 Dissemination and Communication Objectives

The overall objective of the crossCert dissemination concept is to increase the impact of the project among the target audiences. To raise awareness for the project, dissemination activities are extremely relevant during its whole lifecycle and beyond. Beyond the general goals for dissemination identified in the Grant Agreement, the following objectives are relevant:

Table 1 Dissemination and Communication Objectives

Project objectives	What do we do to reach the project goals?	Dissemination and Communication objectives
<p>crossCert main objective: To contribute to the success of the next-generation EPCs by elaborating and testing guidelines and recommendations</p>	<p>Increase knowledge</p>	<p>C&D will inform the target groups about the crossCert recommendations and the guidelines.</p> <p>C&D actions will share the benchmark repository, technical guidelines for the next generation of EPCs, recommendations to create databases for the exploitation of EPC's data, guidelines for the design of people-centred EPCs, and harmonisation of EPCs, with our audience by disseminating relevant project results.</p>
	<p>Influence attitude</p>	<p>C&D will influence experts and policymakers by EPC knowledge exchange centre, an EPC community forum and by cross-testing both existing and forthcoming certificating procedures in more than 140 buildings in ten member countries using capacity building, bilateral and multilateral meetings, events and workshops as tools.</p>
<p>01: Creating a benchmark repository</p>	<p>Raise awareness</p>	<p>C&D will raise the awareness of EPC experts and their organisations about how to reduce the performance gap by facilitating the evaluation of the EPC performance.</p>
	<p>Increase knowledge</p>	<p>C&D will increase the knowledge of EPC experts and their organisations in assessing the performance of the new EPC procedures.</p>
<p>02: Providing technical guidelines for the next generation of EPCs</p>	<p>Increase knowledge</p>	<p>C&D will increase the knowledge of EPC experts and their organisations.</p> <p>C&D will influence experts providing recommendations to reduce the performance gap, to implement the new KPIs in the EPCs, to present the renovation measures to the building owner and to verify and control the EPC quality.</p>

	Influence attitude	C&D will increase the likeliness of experts using technical guidelines in designing relevant solutions for national frameworks and contribute to harmonisation in the EU.
	Change behaviour	C&D aims to support exploitation by the implementation of the new KPIs in the EPCs.
03: Developing guidelines and tools for the exploitation of EPC data	Increase knowledge	C&D will increase the knowledge of EPC experts and their organisations. C&D will influence experts providing recommendations to create databases for the exploitation of EPC's data.
	Influence attitude	C&D will increase the likelihood of experts using tested tools to improve the information EPCs deliver to end-users and to market agents.
04: Elaborating a set of guidelines for the design of people-centred EPCs	Increase knowledge	C&D will increase knowledge of EPC experts and their organisations and policy-makers. C&D will influence experts to enhance the EPCs design for a better user experience.
	Change behaviour	C&D will suggest improvements to the existing training and education of certified EPC issuers and to promote and market the new EPCs.
05: Providing recommendations for the harmonisation of next-generation EPCs	Increase knowledge	C&D will increase the knowledge of EPC experts and their organisations and policy-makers. C&D will influence experts by providing information on the testing and assessment of the current and new EPC approaches, and support policy makers by recommendations on harmonisation aspects related to technical performance, data exploitation and the human factor.
	Change behaviour	C&D aims to support exploitation by providing recommendations for policy makers on harmonisation aspects.
06: Creating an EPC knowledge exchange	Increase knowledge	C&D will increase knowledge of EPC experts and their organisations as well as

centre		<p>policy makers.</p> <p>C&D will influence experts by offering access to a web-based repository of information on EPC approaches.</p>
	Influence attitude	<p>C&D will increase the willingness to implement changes for experts using descriptions of the new EPC schemes and the results of the assessment carried out in crossCert: requirements (software, training of issuers, etc.), performance gap, user-friendliness, exploitation of data, advantages and drawbacks.</p>
	Change behaviour	<p>C&D will support exploitation and provide curated quality information for public authorities to configure the new EPC schemes in their regions/countries.</p>
07: Creating an EPC community forum	Increase knowledge	<p>C&D will increase the knowledge of EPC experts and their organisations as well as policy-makers and users by actively promoting knowledge sharing and acquiring information on new methodologies.</p>
	Change behaviour	<p>C&D will support exploitation by offering a forum of information circulation and thus increase willingness to implement changes by raising awareness on new methodologies.</p>

While the disseminations main approach is sharing the achievements of the project, the communication develops methods in and beyond the process of dissemination of the results. crossCert Communication provides information to convey the project’s key messages through a variety of channels using digital and printed materials, based on the crossCert corporate design with a specific logo, colours and fonts. To present crossCert to the outside world, project partners have the option to use websites, online portals, newsletters, social media channels, press releases as well as documents created in templates for reports and presentations. There will also be a template for the newsletter. An overview of dissemination methods describes the ways we aim to raise awareness, inform the audience, to engage with target groups and to promote the project. This will be followed by explanatory subsections with roadmaps and KPIs.

1.3 Communication Goals

1. Inform the European community about the crossCert outcomes.

2. Inform the stakeholders about the challenges and recommended solutions of improving existing and new EPCs in several member states.
3. Inform the target groups about recommended procedures and guidelines to ensure the quality and value of the new EPCs, and that they meet the new EU requirements.
4. Inform the experts and decision-makers about the results of testing existing and new EPC approaches (dissemination).
5. Inform the experts and decision-makers about suggested improvements to the new EPC approaches through the analysis of the certification experience and results (dissemination).
6. Inform the experts and decision-makers about the guidelines for development of people-friendly EPC products and services integrated with new (and evolving) EPC approaches (dissemination).

1.4 Communication Tools and Channels

The consortium implements classic C&D tools mixed with contemporary communication to reach a variety of goals:

- **Visual Identity** – image building
- **Online Public Relations** – building knowledge, building up publicity
- **Classic Public Relations** – networking, building up target group relations
- **Direct marketing** – dialogue, networking, providing information

The crossCert project consortium plans to reach a specific set of target groups by combining scientific and non-scientific presentations with online media. At relevant milestones of the project, partners will reach out to their contacts to provide crossCert project-related content. While the main hub of the crossCert project will be the crossCert website as a reference point, with access to the benchmark repositories, internet-based EPC Knowledge Exchange Centre and online PR will support dialogue and consultation with the stakeholders of the project. Social online community building will support the content delivery, promoting the idea of peer support and involvement of stakeholders. The support from the H2020 programme of the European Commission will be acknowledged in all dissemination and communication tools and channels.

Collecting personal data via the project digital communication tools

A detailed privacy and cookie policy will be available on the project website. The details of the data management policy are described in Deliverable D1.7 Data management plan and IPR management.

Video conferences and webinars via Zoom by Climate Alliance

Climate Alliance uses Zoom for video conferences and webinars, as it is currently the most appropriate tool for our purposes. Data protection guidelines for Zoom meetings and webinars are published on [Climate Alliance's website](#) and the same rules will apply to Zoom usage in crossCert if organised by Climate Alliance.

Content-based communication

The Communication tools and channels selected take into consideration the target groups and their characteristics. A mailing list for the project newsletters will be created and an action plan for all partners to follow: e.g., dates, deadlines, and responsible people. The promotional material has a clear concept and consistency. Professional design and PR approaches are being implemented. The project

branding is specialised but gives enough space for interpretation thus giving the opportunity to use crossCert branding in various target group channels and in a variety of communication situations. Communication requires concrete actions with concrete products. The term “product” may mean a wide variety of project results. In the case of the crossCert project, the following comprehensive list applies:

- Project visual identity,
- Online and offline databases, Information platforms (crossCert website, Benchmark Repository, Knowledge Center),
- Policy brief,
- Technical guidelines, reports,
- Workshops/seminars/webinars,
- Stakeholder events,
- Cooperation processes and methodologies,
- Know-how and good practices,
- Press releases,
- Social media posts,
- Newsletter articles,
- Website content,
- Reports and analysis papers,
- Scientific publications, and presentations,
- Other publications.

These project results will be communicated according to target audiences involving the following communication channels:

Table 2 Public project results matched with channels and audience

Results	Communication channel	Target audience
Design and results of cross-testing EPCs (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Website ● Newsletter ● Journal publication ● Conferences ● Events 	EPC experts and their organisations, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities.
Repository benchmark (WP2)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Website ● Newsletter ● Conferences ● Events ● Social Media 	EPC experts and their organisations, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities, Academia and the research community.
Technical guidelines for the next generation of EPCs (WP3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Website ● Newsletter ● Conferences ● Events ● Journal publication ● Guidelines publication 	EPC experts and their organisations, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities, Academia and the research

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Media 	community.
Guidelines and tools for the exploitation of EPCs (WP4)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Newsletter • Conferences • Events • Journal publication • Guidelines publication • Social Media 	<p>EPC experts and their organisations, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities,</p> <p>Academia and the research community,</p> <p>EPC users with no expert knowledge.</p>
Tool for the design of people-centred EPCs (WP5)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Newsletter • Conferences • Events • Journal publication • Guidelines publication • Social Media 	<p>EPC experts and their organisations, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities,</p> <p>Policy-makers in the building and energy sector including public institutions with regulatory power on the local, regional and national level,</p> <p>EPC users with no expert knowledge,</p> <p>Academia and the research community.</p>
Recommendations for harmonization (WP6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Newsletter • Conferences • Events • Journal publication • Guidelines publication • Social Media 	<p>EPC experts and their organisations, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities,</p> <p>Policy-makers in the building and energy sector including public institutions with regulatory power on the local, regional and national level.</p>
EPC community forum (WP6) and EPC Knowledge Exchange Centre (WP6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Website • Newsletter • Conferences • Events • Social Media 	<p>EPC experts and their organisations, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities,</p> <p>Policy-makers in the building and energy sector including public institutions with regulatory power on the local, regional and national level,</p> <p>EPC users with no expert knowledge,</p>

		Academia and the research community.
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The value for these main target groups are matched with the envisioned communication methods and paired with the foreseen dissemination value for the target audiences in the following Table:

Table 3 Communication methods paired with value for target groups

Target group	Channels/ Method	Value for target group
Academia research communities	crossCert Newsletters, Peer-reviewed scientific Articles, Website, Social media, Events, Conferences, Online open-access documentation, Webinars, crossCert Outreach Committee.	Share best practices within their field of expertise, Opportunity to communicate with other target groups, Platform to learn and share, State-of-the-art progress through sharing of scientific knowledge, Synergies through cross-project cooperation.
EPC experts and their organisations	Project newsletter, Website, Social media, Documentation, Stakeholder events, Guidelines and tools, Participations at external events, Professional magazines.	Increase awareness and preparedness, Share best practices, services and products, Find out information about crossCert Tools and Guidelines , Receive implementation guidance, Enhance replicability.
Policy-makers	Policy briefs, Outreach Committee, crossCert and partner newsletters, Articles through Press releases, Meetings, Events,	Policy engagement, Increase political legitimacy, Direct and trustworthy information, Awareness-raising on key issues, Knowledge exchange, Exploitation possibility.

	Social media, Project website.	
EPC users with no expert knowledge	Partner newsletters, Articles through Press releases, Meetings, Events, Social media, Project website.	Direct and trustworthy information, Awareness-raising on key issues, Knowledge exchange, Exploitation possibility.

1.5 Dissemination Tools and Channels

crossCert dissemination activities will focus on event-based activities as well as on networking activities targeting committed stakeholders. The partner organisations will participate across multiple dissemination channels to include publications, events and meetings, liaison and clustering events. Key elements of dissemination channels include liaising activities via thematic events as well as digital networking events organised by the project partnership via video-conferencing related to project activities every 6 months. There will be strong networking activities with other institutions and projects on national and EU level, the stakeholder events will engage relevant target groups in creating smooth pathways to implement guidelines and tools. Information will be disseminated over different “energy efficiency measures in buildings” themed newsletters or websites and platforms. The national and regional networks of energy agencies will play a big role here, as well as energy efficiency professionals issuing energy certificates.

Key activities in the dissemination strategy are the EU-wide and national events. Every year the project organises an EU wide event, gathering stakeholders to reflect and feed in latest results and interventions to crossCert activities. Each event will have a dissemination strategy related scope, the first one focusing on networking, the second one on stakeholder engagement, and the third one focusing on dissemination related to policy interventions. National events organised by the partners will enhance national, regional and local impact.

Table 4 Overview of dissemination channels

Dissemination Channels	Objective	Target	Monitoring
Networking events, clustering activities with EU projects	To emphasise the lessons learnt and the best practices compiled; to validate the findings.	Experts, Policy-makers	Number of attendees
Local, national and international stakeholder events	Communicate to the different stakeholders in EU, creating awareness on project results.	All target groups	Event Reports
six-monthly online events	Creating awareness on project results, networking, exchange of information on current developments of the field.	Experts, Policy-makers	Number of attendees
Website	Increasing knowledge on the project topic / Making information easy-to-understand.	All target groups	Google Analytics account set up when the website launched
Newsletters	Making information easy-to-understand & communicating to the different stakeholders in EU and globally.	Academia, Experts, Policy-makers	TYPO 3 Webmail system Partner monitoring tool
Social Media	Creating awareness and familiarity with the project topic, objectives and results.	All target groups	Social Media Monitoring Tool
Press releases	Creating awareness and familiarity with the project topic, objectives and results.	All target groups	Copies of the articles shared on our website
Academic Journal Publications	Creating awareness and familiarity with the project topic, objectives and results.	Academia and research community	Number of Papers published with links to published papers (if applicable: DOI)/Gold
Publication in building themed magazines	Creating awareness and familiarity with the project results.	Experts, Policy-makers	Number of copies distributed and downloaded
Policy Brief/Publishable report	Creating awareness with the project results.	Policy makers	Copies of the articles shared on our website

1.6 Tasks and Responsibilities

In the crossCert project, project partners play a key role in reaching the project’s audience. It is of major importance that partners with direct contact to the project target groups dedicate effort and time to disseminate and communicate project results.

WP Leader (WPL) - CA

Coordinates the activities in collaboration with task leaders and project partners.

Coordinates feedback on the contacts with the stakeholder groups (across the partnership).

Programming and content management of the project website.

Maintains a mailing list to reach stakeholders through the 6-monthly newsletters, gathers content from partners and publishes the newsletter every 6 months.

Identifies dissemination opportunities and ensures partners contribute through networking, presentations and publications.

Ensures all partners contribute actively to the social networks.

Content management of the crossCert social media platforms.

Collects data from partners and writes reports on dissemination activities.

Provides report templates and collects reports on dissemination activities of project partners.

Project Partners (PP)

ALL: Adjust press releases, web content and social media content to their national press, including translation and localization.

ALL: Organise/ Participate and report on events, conferences, workshops, (digital and/or online), campaigns, publications. Partners are in charge of organising outreach activities at national and local level.

ALL: Identify dissemination opportunities (external events, publications) and contribute through presentations and publications and report on participation/contribution.

ALL: Contribute to crossCert website, newsletter and social media, and disseminate newsletters, website, social media in their own channels and in networks potentially interesting for crossCert.

ALL: Inform the European energy community of project activities.

1.7 Time management

Good timing can help make good use of C&D resources. Partners will develop more precise C&D schedules for critical tasks, such as event promotion. Depending on the scale and importance of the event, C&D activities should start 3 months (local training) to 10 or 12 months (high-level policy conference with international participants) before the deadline. The length of the promotion period and the intensity of the event C&D is also dependent on the local traditions with larger countries (e.g. Germany) requiring typically more time and more of a formal approach. The following table defines the checkpoints during the project duration. These phases are subdivided into:

- **Phase 1:** Initial awareness-raising phase (M1-M12),
- **Phase 2:** Engagement phase (M12-M24)
- **Phase 3:** Enabling exploitation phase (M24-M36).

A [GANTT Diagram](#) has been established to provide an overview of the timing of single actions in WP7, and is available online.

WP7 Content Plan	1/22	2/22	3/22	4/22	5/22	6/22	7/22	8/22	9/22	10/22	11/22	12/22	1/23	2/23	3/23	4/23	5/23	6/23	7/23	8/23	9/23	
Project month	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	
Milestones	M1			M3				M2			M4			Interim Report		M6					M5	
Public Deliverables for Dissemination		D7.1		D2.4				D3.1						D2.3				D3.2			D3.3, D3.5	
Newsletters	Content from partners	NL1		Special Issue: Invitation to Next Gen EPC Networking				Content from partners	NL2				Content from partners	NL3		Special Issue: Invitation to Focus Group Event					Content from partners	NL4
Website	Launch	Announce in N, and Social Media		Announce Next Gen EPC Networking												Announce Focus Group Event						
Social Media	Launch	NL1, Events		D2.4	Announce Next Gen EPC Networking			D3.1, Events	NL2, Events					D2.3, NL3, Events		Announce Focus Group Event			D3.2	D3.3, 3.5, Events	NL4, Events	
Digital Networking Events (every 6 months, related to project activities)		Webinar						Webinar						Webinar								Webinar
National Workshops (PPs)		National crossCert Engagement Events																				
crossCert EU Level Events (CA)		Discuss content with partners, invite speakers	find location and check logistics	Announce to stakeholders				Next Gen EPC Networking Event (CA)													crossCert Focus Groups	
CAIC conferences									Hesperange / LUX													Possibly Ireland
Possible events and locations		M6 in BRU or FRA							M15-18, with CAIC													
WP Deliverables		D7.1 (CA)												D7.2 (CA), D7.3 (IR)								
Project meetings																						
Outreach Committee Meetings	done																					

As time passes, more project results will be available for dissemination, thus the hottest phase will be phase 3 with all channels implemented.

Table 5 C&D checkpoints per project phase

Phase	Activities	WP7 Deliverables	Dissemination checkpoints
1	Project website	D7.1: It provides the plan for the project dissemination of results, including channels, activities and materials. (CA) M6	crossCert Web Platform running M5
	Project partners websites		Connect crossCert with all project partners;
	Social media		Establish social media channels for crossCert dissemination;
	Project newsletters		Create communication materials;
	Partner newsletters		Start of crossCert newsletter;
	Stakeholder events		Disseminate crossCert on events and conferences;
	Project Cluster		EU wide event by CA: Next Gen EPC Networking Event M12
Conference presentations	Organise 6 monthly online events		
2	Participation in science outreach activities	D7.2: It provides an update on Year 1 accomplished actions for the project dissemination of results. (CA) M18	Establish networking co-operations with sister projects
	Project website		Feed the crossCert website and social media with crossCert information;
	Social media		Publish further newsletters;
	Project and partner newsletters		Reach out to media;
	Articles		Intensify networking co-operations;
	Conference Presentations		Organise 6-monthly online events
	National and international workshops and events		Publish further scientific publications;
Networking events	Disseminate crossCert on events and conferences;		
3	Participation in science outreach activities	D7.3: Interim Exploitation Strategy: Draft strategy for covering among others the exploitation of the EPCs Knowledge Exchange Centre (IRI-UL) M18 Confidential	EU wide event: crossCert Focus Groups M24
	Project website		Event outreach activities;
3	Participation in science outreach activities	D7.4 Final report on all dissemination and communication activities	Motivate stakeholders and authorities activities.
	Project website		Feed further the crossCert website and social media with crossCert information;

	<p>Social media</p> <p>Project and partner newsletters</p> <p>Articles in magazines specialised on energy efficiency of buildings.</p> <p>Press releases</p> <p>National and international workshops and events</p> <p>Conference Presentations</p> <p>Final Conference</p>	<p>(CA) M36</p> <p>D7.5 Main project outcomes: Short publication with all results (CA) M36</p> <p>D7.6: Exploitation Strategy: final exploitation strategy (IRI-UL) M36 Confidential</p>	<p>Publish further newsletters;</p> <p>Publish press releases;</p> <p>Intensify networking co-operations;</p> <p>Organise 6 monthly online events</p> <p>Publish further scientific publications;</p> <p>Disseminate crossCert on events and conferences;</p> <p>Offer demonstrations,</p> <p>EU wide event by CA: crossCert Policies Conference M36</p> <p>EPC Community activities, exploitation panels;</p> <p>Policy Brief/Short publishable report publication and dissemination. M36</p>
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2 Implementation

This section describes the communication and dissemination of results and activities of the crossCert project as a consortium and of its partners. This process is planned in collaboration with all project partners, supported and monitored by Climate Alliance.

The creation of a common identity and crossCert Communication materials is important for communicating cohesion externally and for providing a sense of unity internally. It can be achieved through the adoption of visual elements such as the crossCert logo, the EU emblem and disclaimer, and a style and a colour set and other graphic elements for the design of virtual dissemination methods such as webinars and presentations, flyers, posters, reports and other dissemination materials. A basic colour set and the crossCert logo set have been developed and adopted at the start of the project. Each partner will be expected to contribute and to cooperate for the achievement of the goals described in this strategy by dedicating appropriate resources for communication and dissemination activities.

2.1 Communication Strategy

Obligatory acknowledgement of EU funding for all public outputs

The following must be included in all dissemination and communication activities:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101033778.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence.

Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. To this purpose, the following text is suggested to be included:

Responsibility for the information and views set out in this document lie entirely with the authors. The European Commission and programme executive agency are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

For more information about acknowledging EU funding see GA articles of 27, 28, 29, 38 and the [Horizon 2020 Online Manual](#) and the instructions included in slides 22-27 the Presentation of WP7 at the kick-off meeting ([WP7 - Project Outreach_crossCert \(CA\).pptx](#)), available [here](#)

Global and local communication for crossCert

Local Communication: Local communication establishes a communication routine with the members of the community, media and stakeholders. First, the communication is used for establishing the necessary connection for participatory processes: engaging with the target groups, stakeholders, EPC experts and their organisations, including experts designing and issuing EPC frameworks, as well as local, national and regional authorities. Second, communication is used for sharing the outcomes of the project dissemination. For better results, long-term cooperation with the interested media outlets and other teams is suggested. Local communication is the responsibility of the project partners. The project message and related materials are suggested to be localised taking into consideration language, culture and local environment related to the building sector, energy efficiency goals and energy performance certification.

Global communication: Global communication aims to inform the international community of experts and decision-makers about the progress and outcomes of the project. Local communication is a responsibility of all the project partners, global communication will be supported by the crossCert communication team and will be coordinated with project partners for amplification. A good representation of different types of actors in the project consortium provides an opportunity to spread the message over the different sectors. Local and global communication, if well-coordinated, can support each other by creating a good mix of local and global content that will be engaging for the local communities and improve the knowledge of global experts.

The communication skillset: Working with the professional communication team helps to be more efficient and avoid costly mistakes. Good communication experts can plan, prepare, design, implement and monitor communication events. Project teams will develop the internal capacity for basic communication work. This includes collecting the media contacts, preparing and publishing press releases, preparing visual presentations (slideshows, posters, infographics, videos), publishing written overviews and analysis, publishing interactive content (web applications, podcasts, films), making and supporting crossCert public events, establishing working relations with media and stakeholder groups, monitoring and reporting the communication actions. Each partner will be represented in the D&C Working group guiding and monitoring the implementation of the present plan.

Time management: Good timing can help make good use of communication resources. Partners will develop more precise communication schedules for time critical tasks like the promotion of events (stakeholder events, seminars, conferences). Depending on the scale and importance of the event, communication activities should start 3 months (local events) to 10-12 months (events with international participants) before the deadline. The length of the promotion period and the intensity of the event

communication is also dependent on the local traditions with larger countries (GB, DE etc.) requiring typically more time and more of a formal approach. It's also important to support time-critical tasks before as well as after the deadline with conclusions, notes, participation statistics etc.

2.2 Visual Identity

The project's visual identity has been developed by Climate Alliance's external graphic designer. A Style Guide was developed to guide the users of the corporate identity in the future use of the visual identity. It contains the rules of using the crossCert logo and defines the crossCert corporate design colours and fonts.

CHAPTER 1 LOGO & POSITIONING

Logo

The Logo consists of the lettering “crossCert” in dark grey half surrounded by a geometrical line consisting of six different colours. If it is necessary for the content, the logo with the claim „Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification“ is used.

		1/2 X
		X
1/2 X		

A safe area should be allowed around the logo whether used for print or electronic purposes. The minimum distance to adjoining objects is 1/2 of the overall height X on all hands.

with claim min. 35 mm

If used with the claim,
the width should be over 35 mm.

Colour type and application

The CMYK logo is available for all print products which are produced in 4C Euroscale print processes. Online and within beamer presentations the RGB version should be applied.

If the logo has to be positioned on a dark background please use the logo with a white safe area around it.

The bw colour logo is used for all basic print products which need to be copied in black and white for example.

Do not stretch!

Do not change colours!

CHAPTER 2 CORPORATE DESIGN COLOURS

Primary colours

The colours used in the logo are the corporate design primary colours.

<p>GREY DARK CMYK 80/50/60/60 RGB 43/63/59 HEX 2B3F3B</p>					
<p>ORANGE</p> <p>CMYK 0/60/97/0</p> <p>RGB 240/125/10</p> <p>HEX F07D0A</p>	<p>RED</p> <p>CMYK 13/91/80/5</p> <p>RGB 204/51/51</p> <p>HEX CC3333</p>	<p>RED BRIGHT</p> <p>CMYK 0/87/100/0</p> <p>RGB 255/51/0</p> <p>HEX FF3300</p>	<p>YELLOW</p> <p>CMYK 10/0/75/0</p> <p>RGB 234/254/103</p> <p>HEX EAFE67</p>	<p>GREEN</p> <p>CMYK 60/0/100/0</p> <p>RGB 102/204/0</p> <p>HEX 66CC00</p>	<p>GREEN DARK</p> <p>CMYK 80/20/100/5</p> <p>RGB 54/137/49</p> <p>HEX 368931</p>
<p>GREY DARK</p> <p>CMYK 80/50/60/60</p> <p>RGB 42/64/59</p> <p>80%</p>	<p>GREY DARK</p> <p>CMYK 80/50/60/60</p> <p>RGB 42/64/59</p> <p>70%</p>	<p>GREY DARK</p> <p>CMYK 80/50/60/60</p> <p>RGB 42/64/59</p> <p>60%</p>	<p>GREY DARK</p> <p>CMYK 80/50/60/60</p> <p>RGB 42/64/59</p> <p>40%</p>	<p>GREY DARK</p> <p>CMYK 80/50/60/60</p> <p>RGB 42/64/59</p> <p>30%</p>	<p>GREY DARK</p> <p>CMYK 80/50/60/60</p> <p>RGB 42/64/59</p> <p>20%</p>

Colours for additional design

For additional design within the corporate design basically colour gradients (grey dark 40% to white) are used. **The primary design colours are used very cautiously.**

CHAPTER 3 CORPORATE DESIGN FONTS

The Barlow type family is used for all texts within print and online crossCert design products. Within the crossCert logo design Barlow is used as well. For your text within word and ppt documents you can use alternatively the Arial font and corresponding font styles and sizes.

Please use the download link: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Barlow#standard-styles>

Barlow - Regular

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ ÄÖÜ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz äöü
.,:!/?&%§(,)„ 1234567890

Barlow - Semi-bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ ÄÖÜ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz äöü
.,:!/?&%§(,)„ 1234567890

Barlow - Bold

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ ÄÖÜ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz äöü
.,:!/?&%§(,)„ 1234567890

FONT COLOURS FONT SIZE

The general font colour is black.

In order to highlight text sections colours (see chapter 2) can be used.

Please notice: the overall look & feel is modern and elegant - use colours cautiously!

Font size running text (default font)

Barlow	regular
Font size	10 pt
Line spacing	14 pt
Tracking	5

Addresses / footnotes

Barlow	regular
Font size	9 pt / 7 pt
Line spacing	12 pt / 10 pt
Tracking	5

Titles

Barlow bold
Font size 18 pt (front page up to 32 pt)
Line spacing 22 pt
Tracking 0

BARLOW SEMI-BOLD
FONT SIZE 12 PT
LINE SPACING 16 PT
TRACKING 0

Barlow semi-bold
Font size 12 pt
Line spacing 16 pt
Tracking 0

Several templates for Word and PowerPoint presentation template have been developed based on the requirements, as well as social media identity materials.

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101033778

17.11.2021

Titel der Präsentation

4

2.3 Dissemination and Communication Activities

While dissemination activities' main approach is sharing the achievements of the project, the communication activities use methods in and beyond the process of dissemination of the results. The time plan of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy will be updated at each reporting period, engaging tools, activities and resources for implementing the crossCert project's dissemination and communication strategy.

Goals – Audience – Project Message – Tools – Tactics

Communication activities are designed using the 'Goals – Audience – Messages – Tools – Tactics' approach, identifying and describing these for the whole project, parts of the project and for the deliverables/outcomes that require dissemination.

Communication Goal: The goal of the activities is to inform the European community about the crossCert project.

Target Audience: The audience consists of EPC experts and their organisations, Policy-makers in the building and energy sector, EPC users with no expert knowledge, and Academia and the research community.

Project Message: To achieve their common goal, all partners will dedicate much effort to disseminating project results at all levels, be it internally by the participating organisations and the consortium, as well as on regional, national, European or international levels. The overall message to be communicated to all target audiences is:

crossCert:

Towards reliable, practical, and people-centred European energy performance certification of buildings.

Keywords: energy efficiency, energy performance certificates, renovation, H2020 research project, buildings, energy policy, building sector. On Social Media: #crossCert #H2020 #energyefficiency #climatechange #EPCs #buildings #energypolicy #fitfor55 #renovationwave #energyexperts

Tools: The tools are stakeholder engagement events, digital platform publications such as the website, social media accounts and other platforms, external events, scientific publications, press releases, a short publishable report at the end of the project, networking activities, newsletters. All tools planned are

outlined in Table 7. Every partner is responsible for his or her communication channels and monitoring results related to crossCert content.

Concrete dissemination activities focus on delivering project results via various dissemination and communication channels in a given timeframe or in a cycle (such as the newsletters or social media). Communication activities include digital materials as well as communication methods such as social media or stakeholder events as well as outreach activities. Both the materials and the events are considered as the backbone of the communication activities. See the structure of the communication and dissemination tools below:

Table 6 Channels and Tools

Digital Channels

Websites (crossCert project website, partner websites)	WPL, PPs	Month 6-36: Regular updates on project progress
Digital project newsletter disseminated via mailing lists and all partners' networks	WPL in EN with input from PPs	Every 6 months, digital archives via website
Online events	WPL with partner contribution	Month 12-36
Social media channels	WPL with partner contribution	Month 6-36
Knowledge Exchange Centre	WP6 lead with contribution of WPL and PPs	Month 24-36

Public events and stakeholder meetings

EU-wide events	WPL with partner contribution	Yearly
National events	All partners	Yearly
Workshops	All partners	From Month 6 on
Conferences, Exhibitions, Fairs,	All partners	Continuous

Networking tools

Interaction with sister projects	All partners	From Month 6 on
Joint events with networks, projects	All partners	Every year from month 6 on

Joint Publications / exchange of articles	All partners	From Month 6 on
Online community on LinkedIn/other platforms	All partners	From Month 6 on

Communication materials

Flyers to inform about the project in English	WPL	Month 3-6
Roll-up and poster in English	WPL with input from PP	Month 3-6
Standard project presentation	WPL	Month 18

Publications

Publications in general: technical and scientific journals	Relevant partners	From Month 12 onwards
Project results in videos/short publications explained	WPL in collaboration with relevant partners	From Month 24 onwards
Project results Publication/including policy brief	WPL	From Month 30 onwards
Publication in magazines related to energy efficiency and building sectors	All partners	Every year

2.3.1 Digital Channels: Websites

A project website is being developed from the early project stages, it is planned to be available from February 2022 on. It will contain all project information (topic, objectives, partners' information), information about the project results, ongoing activities, the links to the Knowledge Exchange Centre and crossCert Repositories as well as all EPC communication channels, such as social media and all project deliverables.

<https://www.crosscert.eu/>

The website is an important dissemination tool as it links to all project material and allows sharing our research. The crossCert website structure and concept was designed by KB, and developed with an external provider. The website is being developed on the TYPO3 and will be managed for 3 active and 2 passive years by CA, relying on all partners for some sections (input to news and events, etc.). It will contain, project information (topic, objectives, partners' information), information about the project topic (definitions, Toolkit, Causal Model, Publications and events), access to and information on open data and all project deliverables. Graphical material will also be shared, as well as links to sister projects, news and events. The website will be dynamic and contain text written in an easy-to-understand format. It will be intuitive, providing well-structured information and regularly updated.

Finally, it will be in English, with selected content & information. All public deliverables will be available for download on the project website. Beyond the project website, all project partners will publish key crossCert results via their own digital frameworks.

2.3.2 Digital Channel: Newsletters

The crossCert newsletter is the project's direct dissemination and communication tool. In the dissemination activity, the newsletter serves as a tool to distribute results and interim results, whereas in communication, it serves as a communication and public engagement tool.

The crossCert newsletter will be published every 6 months starting at M6. The responsible partner (WPL) will ask project partners for information and articles to compose and publish in the newsletters. The information will also be available on a regular basis as posted on social media and the website, the newsletter is a way to gather all news and publications into a single dissemination tool. The project partners are requested to forward the crossCert newsletter to their networks and multipliers or include it as a link or with news in their own newsletters, and share proof in the monitoring tool. Stakeholders and multipliers will be informed about the project objectives and measures, relevant legislation or political initiatives, good practice cases, tools, events, and experiences through electronic newsletters.

For the crossCert newsletter, we established a stand-alone solution in TYPO3 Content Management System with a newsletter plugin, thus connecting the website and the newsletter archives. The layout

will be oriented to the Style Guide and include [an “unsubscribe and subscribe”](#) section which is connected with a subscriber database following the double Opt-In process according to current GDPR standard.

The content is based on several deliverables, project news and news coming from cooperation partners. We will follow the general EU data protection law reasoned by running the project newsletter: subscribers register on the website and tick a box confirming they want to be registered and have read the privacy policy available on the website. An option to unsubscribe at any time will be included in every newsletter. We will make sure that the newsletters content will be published on the crossCert website as well on the international level, the electronic newsletter eClimail of Climate Alliance will be used to disseminate target audience relevant results of the project. All project partners will publish articles in their newsletters. Central elements for dissemination will be the offers of crossCert:

- EPC cross-testing procedure (D2.4) M8
- Technical guidelines for next generation of EPCs (D3.1-7) starting M12
- Review outcomes from projects on new EPC paradigms preceding crossCert (D2.3) M18
- crossCert benchmark repository (D2.8) M26
- Analysis of the current integration of EPC data (D4.2) M26
- Specifications for developing EPC translating tool (D4.3) M29
- Linking next-generation of EPCs to energy audits, logbooks and BRPs (D4.4) M31
- EPCs as facilitators of one-stop shops (D4.5) M33
- Guidelines for training and education of EPC issuers (D5.3) M32
- Guidelines and recommendations toolkit for the development of people-centred EPC products and services (D5.5) M34
- EPC Knowledge Exchange Centre (D6.4) M34
- Recommendations for EPCs harmonisation across Europe (D6.5) M36
- Meetings/webinars/joined workshops with similar EU projects and initiatives
- Conference/Event reports, announcements
- Stakeholder events and publications, External Publication links
- Proceedings and material from EU level events and policy support actions

Table 8 gives an overview of the crossCert newsletters that are planned to be used to disseminate results of the crossCert project, followed by the table of partner newsletters.

Table 7 Newsletters Roadmap

Month	Communication (approximate, depending on availability)	Related External Newsletter
M6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project introduction, ● Announcing: Website, Social Media, EPC cross-testing procedure, Sister Project News, Next-Gen EPC Networking Event, ● crossCert Engagement Events, ● Due Deliverables . 	Project Partner newsletters, Sister project newsletters, Identified partner network newsletters.
M13	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Technical guidelines for next generation of EPCs, ● First EU-wide event: Next Gen EPC Networking Event, ● First national events, 	Project Partner newsletters, Identified partner network

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Due deliverables. 	newsletters.
M18	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review outcomes from projects on new EPC paradigms preceding crossCert, • Materials from the EU and national level events and support actions, • Announcing crossCert Focus Groups, • Events, • Due deliverables. 	<p>Project Partner newsletters, Sister project newsletters, Identified partner network newsletters.</p>
M25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Announcing: crossCert benchmark repository and Analysis of the current integration of EPC data, • Stakeholder Feedback Conference, • Sister project meetings, • Scientific Publications, • Due deliverables. 	<p>Project Partner newsletters, Sister project newsletters, Identified partner network newsletters.</p>
M30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EPC translating tool, • crossCert Policies Conference Events, • Due deliverables. 	<p>Project Partner newsletters, Sister project newsletters, Identified partner network newsletters.</p>
M36	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All results and due Deliverables, • Final Publication, • Recap of the crossCert Policies Conference. 	<p>Project Partner newsletters, Sister project newsletters, Partner network newsletters.</p>

2.3.3 Digital Channels: Social Media and Online Communities

The European Commission and the Horizon 2020 programme are active on social media (especially Twitter) and the projects are welcomed to follow their lead.

crossCert has established accounts on Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn:

- Twitter: [@crossCerth2020project](https://twitter.com/crossCerth2020project)
- Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/crossCert-Project-103708048271029>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/crossCert-project>
- LinkedIn Group: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12583680/>

In addition to global conversation, a local social media presence can be used on more suitable platforms for developing better contact with the local audience (for participatory processes, etc.). We need to be aware that most global social media platforms are international, thus primary communication will take place via the crossCert social media channels with the vision of working together with the project partners’ social media channels. crossCert content will include the acknowledgement and disclaimer to the Horizon programme. Tags to use in crossCert:

#crossCert #H2020 #energyefficiency #EPCs #energy #buildings #efficientbuildings

The project’s social media strategy

The social media channels of project partners will amplify the project’s social media outreach. As it is not possible to engage in all conversations everywhere, crossCert will pick the most important ones initially and will identify the others as the project progresses. We will learn when and when not to engage and will have defined objectives and know exactly what we are trying to achieve with regular social media posts. In the initial phase, crossCert will establish “the brand”. Later on, crossCert will raise awareness and as the project progresses, we will approach policymakers and scientists as well as the ESM community to continue with the work we started.

Partners will define their staff members to post in their mother tongue to the relevant stakeholder group and will consult their own organisations' communication team / social media content manager to collaborate with Climate Alliance's crossCert social media content manager of Climate Alliance.

Develop good content – help and share

crossCert content has to be valuable; otherwise we are just “making noise”. To prepare and share good content, the partners shall be active in picking and communicating relevant content. Social media is not a direct marketing tool, we will share articles, presentations and videos that are relevant – these can be crossCert's or someone else's (credits and links to them will be mentioned). Comments to other discussions will only be added if helpful and relevant.

Four main behaviours will be followed when creating and communicating good content on crossCert:

- Show excitement and celebrate that stakeholder's success in the post.
- Addressing the stakeholder by name adds a personal touch.
- Tell the stakeholders where we found out about their connection to crossCert.
- Leave the pitch open, friendly, concerned, and personable.

Promote content and stakeholder interaction

Just as all organizations now promote their websites in everything they do, so too should social media be promoted. Announcements, posts made on the crossCert [Twitter](#) account, [Facebook](#) page or [LinkedIn](#) profile will be inserted in other communication channels at every opportunity. The website, social media accounts, etc. will be visible on material created for conferences, on news releases and vice versa. Details will be added to slides, news releases, and the social media channels will be posted on the project website. All public presentations will be posted on the social media sites and all offline communications should be integrated with social media, e.g. Twitter, [LinkedIn Group](#) and Facebook announcements about an upcoming conference. Videos and photos of the event and speeches can be uploaded to YouTube.

Integrate online and offline events

The social media team needs to work closely with the project team, as it needs to know what events are happening in advance. As the website is a conduit, we will aim to drive traffic to the website by integrating content first posted on it into the social media workflow. This will be realised by using a posting policy of all news on events and publications that go first online on the website and social media posts are formulated so that they constantly drive traffic to the website by including a direct link. Furthermore, we will consider brief videos and images (depending on the style or the news item) to be tailored for web use. A [shared schedule](#) of events allows integration in the Communication Plan for regular communication channels and social media platforms (like ads, promotions, videos, etc.) will be outlined.

crossCert will watch the analytics set up for the website and for the social media profiles to see if traffic has spikes as a result of any particular posting. Feedback and questions will be processed as soon as possible. Comments will be read and if necessary, reacted to. Interactions will be measured. crossCert Communication channels are synced at all times.

Resources and connections to other communication channels

While a social media publication plan exceeds the capacity of this strategy, the project will work with milestone related content management, thus following the content-based social media posting concept. Publications and important events will be preceded by dedicated campaigns.

A preliminary monthly plan has been set up via the [WP7 GANTT diagram](#) indicating the project results to be communicated via social media content management. The following digital communication channels will be linked to the social media content plan:

- crossCert Newsletters
- E-mails from partners
- E-mails from sister projects
- crossCert Website
- crossCert partner emails
- Partner websites

2.3.4 Public events: Engaging the experts and policy makers

crossCert events will be held as engaging regular public webinars, national stakeholder events and presentations. Furthermore, EU level events will make sure that the results are going public and target groups are involved in the outcomes of crossCert. Climate Alliance will organise a final policy event to validate the crossCert results, while the Climate Alliance conferences and relevant international conferences and events will be attended to ensure wide dissemination of results. Furthermore, upon invitation by the CINEA, the project partners will contribute to common dissemination activities to increase synergies between projects, and the visibility of H2020 and European Commission supported actions. Dissemination in this context will happen by engagement of stakeholders active in sister projects in all activities related and by participating in thematic events with focus on EPCs. This method will be useful to get feedback from experts on particular issues, to generate interest in our crossCert project and to mobilise followers. Furthermore, as the project evolves and the collaboration with networking partners develops, suitable networking partners' representatives will be invited to validate our results.

crossCert will organise regular online **webinars** to engage local and regional public bodies as well as experts that can act as multipliers (especially policy makers). The first pool of stakeholders has been already established by inviting the partners' networks (see 42 Letters of Supports in Section 1.2 and the Annex of the Proposal). Through the local network of partners, regional and national stakeholders may be involved. These events will focus on problems, challenges and good practices related to the EPCs, the themes and formats of each event will be set up following the consultation of all project partners to identify themes and topics that are actual, relevant and important to inform the work in the Work Packages.

National Workshops at the beginning and at the end of the project will ensure that the stakeholders relevant for the project are not only informed but are also engaged in project activities. These workshops will be held by project partners, will focus on local and national input and output and will be informed by the project deliverables.

EU Policy level events will take place once a year and will be organised by the Work Package leader starting with Europe-focused networking events, bringing together national and EU level organisations and experts. The event series will continue to feed in deliverables and plans for the last year during the second year with a Focus Group event, and will finish with a Policy Event at the end of the project to validate the project outcomes. In order to reach a large number of European public authorities being interested in the crossCert results and methodologies, the EU level events will be attached to other external policy-related conferences.

EU level events					
Name	Purpose	When	Where	Participants	Partner responsible
Next Gen EPC Networking Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presenting crossCert and networking - Discussing and shaping up crossCert's contribution in the light of other EPC initiatives - Introducing the crossCert tools, eg EPC Knowledge Exchange Centre 	M12	Same place as project M12 meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinators of other next-generation EPCs EU projects - Representatives of EU associations or national energy agencies of other countries leading similar efforts 	WP7(T7.4) Climate Alliance in collaboration with WP2(T2.1) UZ
crossCert Focus Groups	Discussing status and proposals re: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - extending the value of EPCs to public authorities and potential investors - making EPCs more people-centred - harmonising EPCs across Europe 	M18	Same place as M18 meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leaders of new EPC initiatives, EU projects - European experts in energy certification 	WP7(T7.4) Climate Alliance or one of WP4/5/6 (REGEA/IRI UL/CRES)
crossCert Policies Conference	Discussing guidelines and policy recommendations arising from WP3 to WP6, and meshing them with similar conclusions from other projects and activities	M36	Same place as project final meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinators of other next-generation EPCs EU projects - Representatives of EU associations or national energy agencies of other countries - High-level stakeholders (national certification bodies, ministries) of partner countries 	WP7(T7.4) Climate Alliance
Country level events					
crossCert Engagement Event	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presenting the project - Engaging the local stakeholders - Establishing the status quo - Finding out stakeholder requirements and recommendations - Defining national working groups (e.g. group interested in training of EPCs issuers, group interested in EPC data exploitation) 	M06	Tbd by each partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National stakeholders: local authorities, EPC issuers, regional/national authorities 	National agencies (CRES, REGEA, KAPE, ENEFFECT, MIEMA, EREN, ECN, AEA) under WP7(T7.4)
Stakeholder Feedback Conference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presenting the project draft findings - Getting feedback from local stakeholders for final conclusions 	M30	Tbd by each partner	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - National stakeholders: local authorities, EPC issuers, regional/national authorities 	National agencies (CRES, REGEA, KAPE, ENEFFECT, MIEMA, EREN, ECN, AEA) under WP7(T7.4)

External Conferences and Events

Presentations and conferences are a very efficient dissemination and communication method. Presentations to create awareness of the importance of the crossCert project and are important dissemination activities closely related to the publication of articles for the research partners of the consortium. To attract the interest of potential stakeholders' project partners will participate in at least 15 national, European and international events and conferences. Taking part in this and other events and conferences includes spreading disseminating materials and additionally presentations, scientific publications, conference posters, as well as organising networking activities, in-situ-sessions, workshops. The participation in events and conferences starts from the second year of the project and will be intensified with the finalised dissemination materials to the end of the project (M36).

Currently identified events we consider (list to be amended each year):

- World Sustainable Energy Days (WSED),
- European Energy Efficiency Conferences
- Climate Alliance International Conference
- EU Sustainable Energy Week
- EU Green Week
- European Week of Cities and Regions
- European Energy Network annual meeting
- IEA events - International Energy Agency
- IEW - International Energy Workshop
- ECEEE - Summer Study (Europe Data for Policy (Data for Policy CIC)
- BEHAVE - Conference on Behaviour and EE (Europe)
- SDEWES conference
- EERA JP e3s events.

We are fully aware of the fact that the global pandemic of SARS-COVID-19 puts an extra burden on partners planning to get involved at various events. Originally, it was planned to participate and organise events on a regular basis as project results evolve. With the pandemic, European events have been constantly forced to either cancel their scheduled programme or postpone and transform a face-to-face event into a digital event. The partners will adjust and take into consideration all relevant regulations and safety regulations.

2.3.5 Networking and Sister Projects

Networking activities are an important action to disseminate and communicate crossCert project information and results to our target audience. The partners of crossCert will foster collaboration with other research projects and stakeholders.

WP 7 will support the establishment and communication efforts for Task 6.1 EPC Community. In this task, the partners will first develop the national stakeholders' lists for each participating country and establish the project stakeholders' community as a whole. This community will be the pool of the participants for project activities at the national and European levels. The project will support communication among the stakeholders via a mailing list, social media groups such as the LinkedIn group and other tools; and the EPCs Knowledge Exchange Centre that will be developed in Task 6.2.

International dissemination can be realised by our scientific project partners through participating in international conferences and events, by publishing scientific papers, or by all project partners and by publishing articles and news in worldwide social media. These activities will be established through intense focus on phases 2 and 3.

Organisations and institutions have already been approached by the consortium partners to be involved in networking activities. Out of the over 40 stakeholders with expressed interest in the project, the following 19 will be further involved in project activities via the Outreach committee:

- Ministry for the Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge (Spain),
- Ministry of Construction and Physical Planning (Croatia),
- Ministry of Economic Development (Poland),
- Piraeus Chamber of Commerce and Industry (Greece),
- EnR - The European Energy Network,
- ENERAGEN - The Association of Spanish Agencies for Energy Management (Spain),
- SOFENA - Sofia Energy Agency (Bulgaria),
- Econoler (Bulgaria),
- Bulgarian Energy Efficiency and Renewable Sources Fund (Bulgaria),
- Municipal Energy Efficiency Network EcoEnergy (Bulgaria),
- Black Sea Energy Cluster (Bulgaria),
- Alliance for Energy Efficiency (Bulgaria),
- University for Architecture, Civil Engineering and Geodesy (Bulgaria),
- Association of Heating Appliances Manufacturers and Importers in Poland (Poland),
- Energy Efficiency in Industrial Processes (EEIP) (Belgium),
- MATCH2INVEST (Greece),
- IC consultants ZT GmbH (Austria),
- Oberon Konzeptbau (Bulgaria),
- Passive House Bulgaria.

As a mid-term goal in the project, we aim to involve stakeholders from each project country via the project partners.

Interaction with sister projects

In particular, other projects in the same or similar call will be invited as speakers at the EU level events and to the regular webinars. Moreover, the partners from crossCert will collaborate with stakeholders of the project in workshops or meetings organised by them. In particular, a preliminary set of actions is foreseen to be discussed with sister projects (D²EPC, E-DYCE, EUB SuperHub, iBRoad2EPC, TIMEPAC, and EPC-RECAST):

- Regular cluster calls between the project coordinators,
- Invite each other to the respective advisory boards,
- Joint workshops and special sessions at a suitable conference as well as joint events at EUSEW and the EU Green Week during the duration of the projects,
- Identify common activities on energy performance certificates on a national level,
- Joint events with networks, projects identified and listed in the proposal.

One aim of crossCert dissemination activities is to develop a transnational network effect. Networking events with identified stakeholders will be attended by the crossCert consortium and links to existing initiatives by implementing cross-project collaboration will be exploited as much as possible:

QualDeEPC: Enhanced Energy Performance Certification linked with deep renovation, (H2020, ends 2022); crossCert partners participating: CRES

U-CERT: USER-CENTRED ENERGY PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT AND CERTIFICATION H2020, ends 2022); crossCert partners participating: ENEFFECT, IRI UL

X-tendo: eXTENDING the energy performance assessment and certification schemes via a mODular approach (H2020, ends 2022); crossCert partners participating: CRES, KAPE

ePANACEA: Smart European Energy Performance Assessment and Certification (H2020, ends 2023); crossCert partners participating: CRES

E-DYCE: Energy flexible DYnamic building Certification (H2020, ends 2023); crossCert partners participating: None

D²EPC: DYNAMIC DIGITAL ENERGY PERFORMANCE CERTIFICATES (H2020, ends 2023) crossCert partners participating: AEA

EPC-RECAST: New toolbox to assess building energy performance and retrofit needs (H2020, ends 2023); crossCert partners participating: None

iBROAD (H2020, ends 2020); crossCert partners participating: ENEFFECT, KAPE

ALDREN (H2020, ends 2020); crossCert partners participating: None

TripleA-reno (H2020, ends 2021); crossCert partners participating: IRI UL

eCentral (Interreg Central, ends 2021) crossCert partners participating: REGEA

PrioritEE- PLUS (Interreg Med,); crossCert partners participating: CRES, REGEA, UNIZAR

EFFECT4buildings (Interreg Baltic Sea Region, ends 2020); crossCert partners participating: ECNET

Some crossCert partners are participating (or will participate) in five of these projects, and this will facilitate this information sharing. The crossCert networking activities under WP7 (Task 7.4) will provide a forum for detailed, in-person interactions.

There will be strong networking activities with other institutions on national and EU level (networks of cities like Energy Cities, FEDARENE European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and the Environment, Covenant of Mayors, etc.) to support activities with a crossCert approach. Their members will be informed through different forms of communication (newsletters, news, etc.) about crossCert opportunities. The work package leader has a large database with 3100 contacts to municipalities in Europe. Information will be disseminated over various other newsletters (see first list under “Newsletters”), furthermore, the recently established Working group on Buildings of Climate Alliance will serve as an additional stakeholder engagement possibility to reach municipalities.

Joint Publications / exchange of articles

The established co-operations have to be nurtured the whole project duration by having regular contacts, sending information, newsletters, sharing events where crossCert is represented, news etc. It is an intensive process but very effective. We plan to establish regular calls for submissions for the crossCert newsletter and approach relevant stakeholders for content relevant for crossCert activities. The following roadmap describes a 3-year plan for networking activities:

Table 8 Networking Roadmap

Date	Activity	Communication
M5	Set up a contact list	Project introduction, Mapping networking and Collaboration opportunities with sister projects, relevant content identification Invitation to Public events Call for Articles to NL1
M6	Send Newsletter nr 1 to identified networks	Announcing first National Engagement events and Next Gen EPC EU level event Content summary of public deliverables due to date,
M12	Invitation to Next Gen EPC EU level event, Send Newsletter nr 2,	Announcing public events, Content summary of public deliverables due to date
M18	Participation at network events, Send Newsletter nr 3	Public events, + announcing EU level Focus groups, Content summary of public deliverables due to date
M24	Co-organizing network events, Invitation to policy events,	EU level Focus Groups report Scientific Publications,

	Participation at network events, Send Newsletter nr 4.	Announcing National Stakeholder Feedback Conferences, Content summary of public deliverables due to date,
M30	Invitation to policy briefing, Send Newsletter nr 5, Participation at network events, co-organizing network events,	News around national stakeholder conferences Announcing EU level Policy Conference, Content summary of public deliverables due to date
M36	Send Newsletter nr 6, Invite to policy events, Participate at network events, co-organize network events	Final Publication Final deliverables, Events and Publications, Content summary of public deliverables due to date

2.3.6 Publications

All partners are fully aware of the Open Access policy that applies to scientific publications as stated in Article 29.2 of the H2020 Grant Agreement “Open Access to Scientific Publications”. All peer-reviewed journal (or other) publications arising from crossCert will be made freely and openly available on the project’s website or other online databases/pages (institutional or publishers when applicable). The publications funded by the project and after an embargo period (if necessary), it will be made accessible to the **Knowledge Centre** after their publication. Additionally, research contents are planned to be submitted to the European Open Science Cloud and planned to be promoted via ResearchGate.

Publication in magazines

A major expression of external dissemination is the production of deliverables. Over the entire project duration (M1-M36), the consortium will produce several public deliverables. They will be made publicly available in the project website resources area, social media, if appropriate in the newsletter and press releases in order to spread the project’s excellence and disseminate knowledge to our target groups. Based on the deliverables, articles will be produced for relevant magazines, publication subject to approval.

The Final Publication

The crossCert final publication (D7.5 Main Project Outcomes) will be created at the end of the project, based on the principles of efficiency, good and creative visuals and understandable language. The report is planned to be published in month M36 when all results are at hand and will be a central element of the

final project communication materials. It will be digital and available for download and preliminary will be available on the website.

Press Releases

Media Work with press releases to reach mass media is foreseen at events or in connection with publications that may be interesting for the public of the project. While in the Grant Agreement, the timing for press releases was not tied to major project milestones, press releases will be focusing on interesting and useful content and may be used for press articles.

We need to keep in mind: Press Releases are for the press. We can send them to our colleagues for their information, but this is not their primary purpose. As such, they are a service that we offer to journalists and should be written as such.

Further press releases are foreseen at major milestones and at popular publications such as the publication of the Guidelines for people-centred EPCs, the Recommendations for the harmonisation of next-generation EPCs.

3 Monitoring Communication and Dissemination Activities

Monitoring the quantity, quality and frequency of communication and dissemination activities helps to identify opportunities and also acts as an early warning system to any future problems. The project partners will be involving stakeholders who are directly interested in the project results or are directly influenced by the outcomes of the project and have a vast network of relevant persons in the target group.

At a later stage of the project, our target groups will be asked to give feedback on project results or even post a review. This way the more engaged stakeholders identify themselves by their own self-selection. A stakeholder who does not care about the project result is likely to be less committed or less emotionally attached. On the other hand, a stakeholder who is engaging is likely to be more emotionally connected. The partners need to know about the opinion and affinity our target groups have towards the project.

This is often expressed through repeat participation, visits, downloads, ratings, reviews, blogs, discussion forums and, ultimately, their likelihood to recommend a colleague. Important questions we have to ask regularly:

- Is stakeholder engagement measured?
- Do we identify the engaged stakeholder and use their feedback to improve communication? If yes, can this stakeholder be engaged through the project lifetime and become a project ambassador?
- Is it possible to increase some stakeholders' level of engagement by moving them up from giving a rating, to writing a review, to joining a discussion, to suggesting ideas, to screening ideas, to testing ideas and eventually to using the ideas when they become policy recommendations? Many of these stakeholders will become "ambassadors" for crossCert and can be engaged beyond the project lifetime to replicate crossCert results.

3.1 Evaluation of the Impact

Good dissemination action effectiveness depends on communication effectiveness. The consortium can measure the project's communication by assessing the effectiveness of each tool the partners used. Within the work package, partners will keep records of dissemination actions, report them via a monitoring tool. [The monitoring tool](#) is available in the shared data management area and partners will be asked to use it on a regular basis, preferably after each dissemination action but at least in each progress report. Furthermore, Project Partners will have the chance to use the Event Template (see Annex 2) to track and monitor their events. The Event template is tied to the monitoring tool in the reporting process and allows CA to gather relevant evidence to be included in the reporting process towards the European Commission.

Communication activities are constantly monitored by the project partners recording the events and evaluating the impact: number of unique visitors, page views, readers, etc. Impact estimation is compiled and reported using the monitoring tool available in crossCert Google Drive cloud service. Partners are responsible for collecting and providing media samples to justify the communication

activities. Partners are specifying the number of Dissemination and Communication activities linked to the project for each of the following categories:

Summary of Target Audience Reached

Date: Month 18

Category	Target audience (estimated numbers of persons reached)									Number of activities
	Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	Industry	Civil Society	General Public	Policy Makers	Media	Investors	Customers	Other	
Organisation of a Conference										
Organisation of a Workshop										
Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularised publication)										
Press releases										
Exhibition										
Flyer										
Training										
Participation to a Conference										
Participation to a Workshop										
Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop										
Video/Film										
Brokerage Event										
Pitch Event										
Trade Fair										
Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects										
Other										
Total	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

3.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Results	Dissemination channel	Target audience	KPIs*
Design and results of cross-testing EPCs (WP2)	Website Newsletter Journal publication Conferences Workshops	National/regional certification bodies Energy agencies Researchers	>20 Certification bodies > 70 Energy agencies > 300 Researchers
Repository benchmark (WP2)	Website Newsletter Conferences Workshops	National/regional certification bodies Energy agencies Researchers EPC issuers Energy auditors	> 20 Certification bodies > 70 Energy agencies > 300 Researchers > 500 EPC issuers > 500 Energy auditors
Technical guidelines for the next generation of EPCs (WP3)	Website Newsletter Conferences Workshops Journal publication Guidelines publication	National/regional certification bodies Energy agencies Researchers EPC issuers Energy auditors	> 20 Certification bodies > 70 Energy agencies > 300 Researchers > 500 EPC issuers > 500 Energy auditors
Guidelines and tools for the exploitation of EPCs (WP4)	Website Newsletter Conferences Workshops Journal publication Guidelines publication	National/regional certification bodies Energy agencies Researchers Public authorities Professionals in the construction sector Financing providers Sectoral associations Energy auditors EPC issuers	> 20 Certification bodies > 70 Energy agencies > 300 Researchers > 250 Public authorities > 250 Professionals in the construction sector > 100 Financing providers > 50 Sectoral associations > 500 Energy auditors > 500 EPC issuers > 200 Building owners

		Building owners Citizens	> 1000 Citizens
Tool for the design of people-centred EPCs (WP5)	Website Newsletter Conferences Workshops Journal publication Guidelines publication	National/regional certification bodies Energy agencies Researchers Professionals in the construction sector EPC issuers Energy auditors Building owners Citizens	> 20 Certification bodies > 70 Energy agencies > 300 Researchers > 250 Professionals in the construction sector > 500 Energy auditors > 500 EPC issuers > 200 Building owners > 1000 Citizens
Recommendations for harmonization (WP6)	Website Newsletter Conferences Workshops Journal publication Guidelines publication	National/regional certification bodies Energy agencies Researchers	> 20 Certification bodies > 70 Energy agencies > 300 Researchers
EPC community forum (WP6) and EPC Knowledge Exchange Centre (WP6)	Website Newsletter Conferences	National/regional certification bodies Energy agencies Researchers Public authorities Professionals in the construction sector Financing providers Sectoral associations Energy auditors EPC issuers Building owners Citizens	> 20 Certification bodies > 70 Energy agencies > 300 Researchers > 250 Public authorities >250 Professionals in the construction sector > 100 Financing providers > 50 Sectoral associations > 500 Energy auditors > 500 EPC issuers > 200 Building owners > 1000 Citizens

**Note that the numbers in each KPI refer to the overall project, that is: In total, throughout the overall project, the KPIs are: 20 certification bodies, 70 energy agencies, 300 researchers etc.*

Communication activities	KPI
Project logo / Visual identity	Available on month 02
Newsletter	One every 6 months
Website	Available on month 05
LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Researchgate	> 1000 contacts
Attendance to conferences, events, workshops	> 15
Events organised by crossCert (workshops, webinars, etc.)	> 30
Knowledge exchange centre	Operational on month 15
Press publications	> 20
Articles published in scientific journals	> 5

4 References

crossCert Outreach GANTT: https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1Z5Kf_ST-dzlc2XX_2-TVyvs8fPCI030WYmm-7yEAJ-w/edit?usp=sharing

crossCert Outreach Monitoring Tool: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/10jr-2AJ8-If741qBwtlXpFqu6AyVkJcTpVdqlhcsphU/edit?usp=sharing>

Climate Alliance Data Protection and Zoom Guidelines, <https://www.climatealliance.org/zoom-and-data-protection.html>

Presentation of WP7 at the kick-off meeting: https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1b2mefEZtHlyn-8jitpk7slgtv6t1mkC7wDweZn_uM8c/edit?usp=sharing

crossCert LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/crossCert-project>

crossCert LinkedIn Group: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12583680/>

crossCert Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/crossCert-Project-103708048271029>

crossCert Twitter: <https://twitter.com/PCrosscert>

crossCert Website: <https://www.crosscert.eu/>

The Horizon 2020 Online Manual: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/acknowledge-funding_en.htm

Sister Projects:

E-DYCE: Energy flexible DYnamic building Certification, <https://edyce.eu/>

D²EPC: DYNAMIC DIGITAL ENERGY PERFORMANCE CERTIFICATES, <https://www.d2epc.eu/en>

ePANACEA: Smart European Energy Performance Assessment and Certification, <https://epanacea.eu/>

EPC-RECAST: New toolbox to assess building energy performance and retrofit needs, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/893118>

QualDeEPC: Enhanced Energy Performance Certification linked with deep renovation, <https://qualdeepc.eu/>

U-CERT: USER-CENTRED ENERGY PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT AND CERTIFICATION, <https://u-certproject.eu/epc-sister-projects/>

X-tendo: eXTENDING the energy performance assessment and certification schemes via a mOdular approach, <https://x-tendo.eu/>

5 Annexes

Annex 1 Visual Identity Tools

Presentation Template

Deliverable Template

Next-generation of Energy Performance
Assessment and Certification

DX.X Title of the deliverable

Task X.X XXXX
WPX XXXX

Authors: XXX
Date: XX/XX/2021

crossCert: Cross Assessment of Energy Certificates in Europe
Grant Agreement (GA) No: 101033778
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Roll-up

crossCert
Next-generation of Energy Performance Assessment and Certification

**Towards reliable, practical,
and people-centred European energy
performance certification of buildings.**

www.crosscert.eu

@PCrosscert

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101033778

Universidad Zaragoza

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KAPE

KAPICRES
ΚΕΝΤΡΟ ΑΝΑΠΕΡΑΣΙΜΩΝ ΓΗΓΕΩΝ ΚΑΙ ΟΙΚΟΝΟΜΙΚΗΣ ΕΝΕΡΓΕΙΑΣ

REGA

IRI UL
Institute for Energy Efficient Buildings
University of Applied Sciences

MIEMA

AUSTRIAN ENERGY AGENCY

EnEffect

EREN

Junta de Castilla y León

EC Network

Climate Alliance

Annex 2 Event Registration Consent to Processing of Personal Data

The following text and consent functionality is to be added to event registration forms:

Consent to Processing of Personal Data

crossCert Project

IMPORTANT:

I consent to the crossCert Project recording this seminar /workshop/ webinar/ conference/ meeting for documentation purpose and publishing these recordings on the internet (eg. but not limited to: crossCert website, crossCert Social media channels).

I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept as an archive of the crossCert Project. The crossCert Project has the obligation to keep its archive until the end of the statutory retention period.

Yes

No

Your rights

You have the right to request to see a copy of the information we hold about you and to request corrections or deletions of the information.. You can revoke your consent at any time by sending a letter to the <ENTER ORGANISATION NAME; ADDRESS> or an e-mail to <ENTER E-MAIL ADDRESS>, without affecting the lawfulness of processing executed due to the consent until revocation. In this case your images and recordings will not be used in future publications but may continue to appear in publications already in circulation.

In case you do not consent to being recorded, please discuss your concerns with us.

I have read and accept the privacy statement <LINK TO THE WEBSITE DATA PROTECTION PAGE>.

ABOUT CROSS ASSESSMENT OF ENERGY CERTIFICATES IN EUROPE: crossCert PROJECT

Towards reliable, practical and people-centred energy performance certification in buildings

CrossCert aims to contribute to the success of the next-generation EPCs (Energy Performance Certificates) by elaborating and testing guidelines and recommendations that will achieve:

- Improved accuracy and usability of the certificate;
- A people-centred design and satisfactory user experience;
- Increased homogeneity across Europe.

This Horizon 2020 project will create a product testing methodology for the new energy performance certificate of buildings approaches. The crossCert project will:

- (1) Cross-test among energy authorities of current Energy Performance Certificates and the new approaches/concepts/initiatives, using more than 140 buildings in 10 European countries, and creating a public benchmarking repository of test cases;
- (2) Compare and analyse the results between different approaches;
- (3) Elaborate of policy recommendations, which will include potential improvements on the accuracy, usability and harmonisation;
- (4) Engage networks and alliances for analysis and for outreach.

How crossCert will achieve its aims

The project will build on exchange of knowledge among European stakeholders on existing and new EPCs in several member states. This exchange will include a wide cross-certification exercise among European countries, and the deployment of an internet-based EPC Knowledge Exchange Centre. The partners will recommend procedures and guidelines to ensure the quality and value of the new EPCs, and that they meet the new EU requirements. This procedure will consist of the evaluation of the new EPCs indicators (such as accuracy, data integration, replicability, understandable, verifiable, or data exploitation). A methodology will be created to assess them in a quantifiable manner. The new EPC approaches will be improved through the analysis of the certification experience and results, and will be tested along the existing and new EPC. Guidelines for development of people-friendly EPC products and services will integrate new (and evolving) EPC approaches and capacity for tailored application on the level of individual EU member states. At the project end, new practises and features will be recommended to achieve the end-user acceptance of next-generation EPCs. This will be achieved by cross-testing both existing and forthcoming certifying procedures in more than 140 buildings in ten member countries.

Our results:

- A public benchmark repository,
- Technical guidelines for the next generation of EPCs,
- Guidelines and tools for the exploitation of EPC data,
- Guidelines for people-centred EPCs,
- Recommendations for the harmonisation of next generation EPCs,
- An EPC knowledge exchange centre,
- A web-based repository of information on EPC approaches,
- An EPC community forum.

Social Media:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/PCrosscert>

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/CrossCert-Project-107761245061962>

Linkedin: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/crossCert-project>

LinkedIn Group: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12583680/>

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nor the European Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Annex 3 Event Report Template

Event Report - crossCert

Full name of the partner

Please, copy/paste the table below as many times as many events you report in the Monitoring Tool.

Title of dissemination/networking action	
Date	dd.mm.yyyy – dd.mm.yyyy
Related Publication and/or Weblink:	
Number of Participants:	
Target Group:	<p>Please select, and delete the NOT relevant groups.</p> <p>Scientific Community</p> <p>Industry</p> <p>Civil Society</p> <p>General Public</p> <p>Policy Makers</p> <p>Media</p> <p>Investors</p> <p>Customers</p> <p>Other</p>
Type of Activity:	<p>Please select, and delete the NOT relevant groups. Add categories if not listed:</p> <p>Distribution of printed flyers</p> <p>Presentation/session at external conferences and exhibitions;</p> <p>Synergies with other EU funded projects</p> <p>crossCert Event (please, specify)</p> <p>Workshop</p> <p>Seminar</p> <p>Other Face-to-face project events</p> <p>Webinar</p> <p>Online meeting</p> <p>Networking event</p>
Venue/location:	Please, add exact venue, or If online action, add the direct web link here:
Topic:	Please, describe here the topic of the action (e.g., in case of conferences, the title and domain of the conference)
Involvement:	Please, describe the ways how crossCert is involved in this activity.

Detailed description:	Please, give a detailed description of this activity. In case the activity is related to e-mailing, please give details on: type of information (press release, invitation to an event, etc.)
Feedback:	Please, describe how you collect feedback, and send a feedback summary for reporting.